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“The role of the President of the Republic of Macedonia in promoting interfaith dialog”

Xhemail Çupi, Master of Diplomacy

South East European University – Tetovo

Abstract

The conflict of 2001 changed the course of interethnic and interreligious harmony in the Republic of Macedonia. This situation was at first understood by the former president Boris Trajkovski, who was methodist evangelist, who did not belong to any of the two polarized communities, Orthodox and Muslim, and with international assistance initiated for the first time the interfaith dialogue.

This practice of weak influence was inherited by the succeeding president, Branko Crvenkovski, and this impact almost disappeared completely during the mandate of president Gjorgji Ivanov. Today, the current problem is the issue of the consensual president; this led to other early parliamentary elections. Does it mean that by electing the same president we will have the same political stalemate and religious disharmony?

Through this research, my goal is to discuss the role of the President in promoting interfaith harmony and to emphasize the importance of the consensual president accepted by both ethnic and religious majority. All the presidents of the Republic of Macedonia will be the case study in this research. The comparative method will be used to evaluate their policies on promoting interfaith harmony and notably the impact of these policies on society.

The results of this research show that the success of a consensual president in easing ethnic and religious tensions arises when he thinks beyond the narrow party interests.

The interethnic and interreligious dialogue should be a priority for the Government of the Republic of Macedonia because the future of this multi-ethnic and multi-religious country depends on it, and this priority has a direct relationship with the election of the consensual president taking into consideration not only the ethnicity but culture and religion as well regarding his election.

Key words: War of 2001, interfaith dialogue, consensual President, intercultural conferences, political crisis.

Discussion

Macedonia is a multiethnic, multicultural and multireligious country. Macedonia's situation is similar to many other European countries where ethnic groups are practically in harmony with religious communities and where interethnic and religious issues are strongly linked with each other, where the reason for this is that the majority of ethnic Macedonians are of Orthodox confession whereas the majority of ethnic Albanians are of Muslim confession. Article 9 of the Constitution of the Republic of Macedonia (1991), states that citizens of the Republic of Macedonia are equal in their freedoms and rights, regardless of sex, race, color of skin, national and social origin, political and religious beliefs, property and social status, while Article 19 states that the Macedonian Orthodox Church, the Islamic Religious Community, the Catholic Church, the Evangelical Methodist Church, the Jewish Community and other Religious communities and groups are separate from the state and are equal before the law and are free to establish schools and other social and charitable institutions, under a procedure regulated by law, according to the same article, where the state guarantees the right to express one's faith freely and publicly, individually or with others and in the end, Article 48 of the Constitution states that members of religious communities have the right freely to express, foster and develop their identity and community attributes, and to use their community symbols; furthermore, the state guarantees the protection of ethnic, cultural, linguistic and religious identity of all communities.

In the Balkans, religion itself has never been the primary cause of continuous conflicts, but although the Balkans has not experienced the kind of wars fought over religion in Central and Western Europe, religion played an important role in ethnic conflicts (Xhaferaj, 2007). Vangjeli (2010: 4) argues that the Macedonian ethnic nationalism has traditionally been inclined to connect with the church, so the Macedonian Orthodox Church is considered not only as a religious organization but also ethnic. In the case of Albanians, although religion is included gradually as an important aspect of ethnic identity, the Albanian national movements in Kosovo and Macedonia were not a priori based on Islam.

According to the international report on religious freedom in the Republic of Macedonia (US Department of State, 2013), ethnic tensions have occasionally affected negatively on the religious freedom because there is a mutual relationship between ethnic and religious affiliation, because most Orthodox Christians are Macedonians and the majority of Muslims are Albanians. According to a report (Global IDP Project, 2004: 10,11), there are different factors that divide the two main ethnic groups in the Republic of Macedonia: Macedonians and Albanians belong to different cultures and religions; They speak different languages and have minimal interethnic communication; There are very few mixed marriages; They live in geographically separated areas, even in multiethnic cities, such as in the capital Skopje, where Macedonians and Albanians live in separate neighborhoods, stay in different cafes and meetings places; They read different newspapers that mainly address their population; Even after doubling the number, over the past two years the number of Albanian civil servants is minimal; They operate in different economic spheres; There are often cases of discrimination and other violations of human rights documented by organizations like Human Rights Watch, Amnesty International and the Helsinki Commission, and these cases are mostly reported by the Albanian side, and as a result, there is a growing sense of distrust towards the state among the Albanians; The war in Kosovo has contributed to widening the gap further between ethnic groups; During the war in Kosovo, the Albanians sympathized with their Kosovo brothers, while Macedonians sympathized with the Serbs for two main reasons; first, for fear that a Kosovo dominated by Albanians will be able to give rise to Albanian nationalism in Macedonia and the second, the influx of hundreds of thousands refugees from Kosovo could destabilize the country and change the demographic balance in favor of the Albanians.

As a result of this divergence, Macedonia faced an armed conflict on its territory in 2001 between the two entities, Macedonians and Albanians. This conflict changed the course of ethnic and religious harmony in the country. The conflict between them was growing day by day, the social situation began to get polarized seriously and there was a real possibility of a civil war. Although the conflict took place mainly along ethnic lines, a certain element of religious tension was included. The special emissary of the General Assembly of the United Nations (Jahangir,

2009) during the mission in Macedonia reported that the ethnic and religion affiliations are separate identities, but they often overlap each other, and this is a specific case in the Republic of Macedonia.

The late President Boris Trajkovski, Methodist Evangelist that did not belong to either of the two major religious communities in the country, Orthodox and Muslim, was the key person who perceived this political crisis, which was about to escalate into civil war. During the war of 2001, the Macedonian Orthodox Church had expressed disbelief in his abilities, and one of the reasons was because of the fact that he was a Protestant pastor (Gjorgevski, 2002). But this did not stop him during this period, with the help of international support, for the first time to initiate the policy of intercultural dialogue, with particular attention to the interfaith dialogue. The new president, Boris Trajkovski, who was generally known as an honest and principled politician, but without the political experience or international connections of the first president of the Republic of Macedonia, Kiro Gligorov (Pettifer 2001: 15), at a critical point of the conflict, visited the United States of America and requested their help in bringing peace to the country (Daskalovski 2004: 3). During his official visit to the United States, he was invited to make a presentation at the U.S. Institute of Peace, and at that meeting, during the speech he asked their help in promoting interfaith dialogue as a means of building peace in Macedonia (Smock 2006: 31).

The conflict of 2001 with the international support ended with the Ohrid Agreement, an agreement that included constitutional changes to the language issue and public representation, which will build a multiethnic and multicultural society including the acceptance of multi-religious aspects. There were constitutional amendments in early November 2001, and on November 16, 2001, in a voting urged by internationals, the Assembly of the Republic of Macedonia adopted constitutional reforms giving the same equal rights as for the Macedonian majority to the "minor" current ethnic population, with special emphasis on the Albanian people who are autochthonous in the Republic of Macedonia. But there was a need for a great willingness by the parties involved, Macedonians and Albanians, and a sacrifice from the governmental partners to implement this agreement. As a result, there was a need of a link connecting them and this role could be best made by the President. Former President Boris

Trajkovski realized the need for this dialogue, as well as its potential to promote the welfare of people not only in the Republic of Macedonia but in the Southeast European region as well. He was an enthusiastic supporter of the efforts of religious leaders and their followers to find ways and means to work with each other to achieve this noble goal. This was accomplished by professor Leonard Suidler and professor Paul Mojzes, leaders of the international dialogue between scholars and magazine editors of ecumenical studies in Philadelphia (USA), where they visited Macedonia six times in a row invited from President Trajkovski (Mojzes, 2004: 135). The latter, after receiving the approval of the U.S. Institute of Peace to intervene in Macedonia, invited the two above-mentioned researchers based on their experiences of Jewish-Christian-Muslim dialogues made in many countries, to come to Macedonia and help organize interfaith dialogue. While Suidler (2008: 4) was holding a dialogue in the city of Jakarta (Indonesia) in February 2000 in the presidential building, his friend and colleague, Paul Mojzes, received an invitation from President Trajkovski since Macedonia needed an intervention because of the ethnic and religious unrests and conflicts. With the help of President Trajkovski, Mojzes and Suidler first visited Skopje in June 2001. During their agenda, they met with the representatives of the five religious communities and set the date of the conference in November the same year. Through this dialogue, they hoped to achieve the two main points: the inclusion of more clergymen in this dialogue, organization of seminars where worldwide scholars of three religions will participate and as a result, when the religious leaders in this dialogue will witness international attention, they will accept the proposals of these meetings. The author Smock (2006: 31) was among the ones who said that leaders of religious communities initially distanced themselves from this process as they thought it was very public and rapid action, but the truth was that all religious communities needed assistance from the international factor to pass the stalemate between them caused by politics, and by the worsening of the political and military situation in the country the dialogue was forced to be further postponed. After the intervention of NATO troops that autumn, Mojzes and Suidler visited Skopje one more time in order to convince again all religious leaders to continue the dialogue. In the end, it was decided that the meeting will take place in May 2002 (Suidler, 2008: 4). After interventions were made by the special representatives, it was noted that religious communities were now ready to work together

in the process of building self-confidence, therefore with the financial support of the U.S. Institute for Peace and the Open Society Foundation they organized a major international conference of the dialogue between Jewish-Christian-Muslim in May 2002 in Skopje which was attended by 50 world religious scholars of the Jewish, Christian and Muslim religion and 150 participants invited from Macedonia, including the President of the Republic of Macedonia and the leaders of the Macedonian Orthodox Church, Islamic Religious Community, Catholic Church, United Methodist and Jewish Community. The conference was entitled "Confidence-building between the churches and religious communities in Macedonia." From Mojzes's point of view (2004: 135), one of the concrete results of this conference was the creation of the Inter-Religious Cooperation Council, consisting of five religious communities in Macedonia. Meetings and seminars were held in the Macedonian Orthodox Faculty, the Faculty of Islamic Sciences at St. Cyril and Methodius University, the University of Tetovo and other civic locations. President Trajkovski himself had a great interest in these meetings and was present at the opening and closing sessions of the conference, as were the leaders of all five main religious communities. President Trajkovski decided to further promote such dialogues in the regional aspect, so he organized a conference entitled "Dialogue among civilizations" in August 2003 in Ohrid. He invited the presidents of the former Yugoslavia countries that have recently been at war with each other, as well as the presidents of Albania, Bulgaria and Hungary. It is amazing that all the presidents of opposing countries during their public speaking said that if the method of dialogue had been used, then maybe wars could have been avoided (Mojzes 2014: 41). More than 300 delegates from around the world returned to their homes with new hopes for the fact that interreligious dialogue can make a difference in achieving respect and peace. They closed the conference with this statement: "We Jews, Christians and Muslims now live in a global village where every person is faced with religious pluralism" (Swidler, 2008: 4).

After the tragic death of President Trajkovski, the successive governments in Macedonia decided to continue and broaden further these dialogues, and with the help of UNESCO they organized a series of world conferences on interfaith dialogue, with several hundred participants from many countries and religions of the world in 2007, 2010 and 2013, but the question if these

conferences have had those impacts as the first conference that was organized at the request of President Trajkovski, will be addressed in the continuing discussion of this paper.

His practice was inherited by the succeeding president Branko Crvenkovski, who also supported the process of interfaith dialogue and cooperation but it was not in the level of his predecessor. In October 2004, Crvenkovski invited foreign scholars who were experts of dialogues who also met the heads of all religious communities in a joint press conference in Ohrid. Thus, religious leaders and scholars from the three religions in the Republic of Macedonia joined with each other and with other international advisers for the continuous quest for peace and understanding, in order to continue the "extensive dialogue" in the country (Mojzes 2004). The special rapporteur on human rights at the United Nations (Jahangir, 2009) welcomed the fact that interfaith meetings are held regularly at a local level; moreover, the Government initiative in organizing the World Conference on Dialogue among Religions and Civilizations held in October 2007 is another indication of its commitment to increase the freedom of religion or belief. According to him, the dialogue, mutual understanding and respect visualized the need to mobilize political and religious leaders, intellectuals and all other actors of society, wherefore, the commitment for the dialogue among civilizations and religions was at the same time a commitment against terrorism and instability.

Dissatisfaction with President Crvenkovski in the Muslim community was born when he decorated the head of the Macedonian Orthodox Church on the occasion of 40th anniversary of the MOC (MIA, 2007). Despite this, one thing is certain according to author Smock (2006: 34), Macedonia has avoided a civil war, mainly due to the political leadership of President Trajkovski, his successor President Crvenkovski, the Assembly of the Republic of Macedonia and the assistance of the diplomatic representatives of the international community, especially the United States and the European Union.

The mandate of President Gjorge Ivanov, despite his attempts and his government to stand in the same line as that of his predecessors, can be considered a retraction from religious and intercultural harmony. During the Ohrid Conference in 2010, and with the absence of the

representatives of the Greek and Bulgarian Orthodox Churches and the general patriarchate in Istanbul, where the Serbian Orthodox Church only sent monk Peter from the diocese of Zvornik - Tuzla considered close to MOC (mesazhi.com, 2010), there were clear signs that interreligious dialogue is not taking its proper form. During the conference held in 2013 in Skopje, unlike previous conferences where churches of neighboring countries did not attend, the Muslim delegation of Macedonia decided not to attend the conference because the government neglected their demands several times. This dissatisfaction of IRC has been reported several times in the report on international religious freedom in Macedonia (US Department of State, 2013) which states that "the Islamic Religious Community once again failed to regain the rightful use of several mosques that the government had agreed to return. Besides, the Islamic Religious Community went on to state that in some cases the government blocked the process of returning its properties by selling them or starting new construction on the disputed property or by disputing the historical legal claim of the IRC for the religious properties. "As a result, IRC boycotted the international conference on interfaith dialogue sponsored by the Macedonian government in May 2013 due to prejudices perceived by IRC that the government has taken a stand against IRC, such as the projects on reconstruction and property restitution. Many analysts encourage religious communities not to participate in forums and interreligious conferences because the international factor will think that everything is all right in Macedonia; hence, it conflicts with what we see every day in the media, while others specifically encourage the Islamic Religious Community not to participate in the dialogue until their demands are met for restitution of the temples' properties, but there are others who oppose such an attitude like the expert on dialogues for Macedonia, Mojzes (2014: 41) who states that this is a wrong decision because it prevents Muslims in Macedonia to share their complaints and aspirations with others. The Institute for Democracy (Societas Civilis, 2014) conducted a survey in June 2014 regarding the evaluation of citizens for the boycott of the Assembly by the opposition in the Republic of Macedonia. The survey of the Institute for Democracy was conducted from 1 to June 30 with over 1100 citizens surveyed straightaway. The survey questions that need to be analyzed because they have direct connection to the president of the state are questions 8 and 9. Question 8 says: "Which institution is more responsible for the improvement of the political dialogue in the

society?” 37.9% of surveyees think that this should be done by the government and ministries, 27.3% by the Assembly and its representatives, 13.0% by the President of the country, 11.9% did not know and 9.9% by the municipalities. Question 9 says: “Which of the following institutions can have a greater role in easing interethnic incidents?” 27.1% of surveyees think that this role belongs to the political parties, 26.7% to the government and ministries, 14% to municipalities, 13.2% to the Assembly and its representatives, 11.0% to the President of the country and 8.1% did not know the answer. As a result, we can conclude that citizens do not believe that the President of Macedonia can improve the political dialogue in the society and can positively affect in relaxing ethnic incidents.

In 2014, on the eve of presidential elections, the public opinion in the Republic of Macedonia was faced for the first time with the idea of a consensual president, but before we can talk in general about the consensual aspect, it is appropriate to explain that to achieve this consensus there is a need of sufficient political culture in society as well as in the political system, because the political systems and attitudes of political leaders are dependent on social and political affiliations of their citizens. Each nation has its own political norms that affect the way people think and reflect about politics, so we can conclude that the way how political institutions operate partly reflects the attitudes, norms and expectations of society. The political culture is a complex and dynamic phenomenon; it is in constant motion and changes with time and space. According to the author Elazar (Almond et al., 2008), there is another division of political culture among others: consensual or conflictual political culture. The consensual political culture is present when people tend to agree on making decisions and solving problems, where most people tend to agree on appropriate ways of making decisions and tend to agree on what are the greatest problems of society, whereas the conflictual political culture is present when the citizens are divided into two regimes for solving major problems. The author distinguishes a third political culture entitled "subculture" that according to him it is present when the separation of two groups (ethnic, religious, ideological, cultural, etc.) is deepened even more and this division has real chances of turning into violence and war. Sometimes, historical or social factors will generate a cultural trajectory such as: ethnic, religious or linguistic identities, migration etc. He

also defined the subculture politics as a "pattern or particular orientation of political action in which it is embedded every political system. Each of these subcultures sees the role of the government in different ways, partly driven by the perception of government as a service and partly from the influence of religion on the moral and standards of population (Hunter, 2011: 18). In Macedonia, the consensual political culture cannot be expressed for the moment, and this was evidenced in the last presidential elections, but we are dealing with conflictual political culture because citizens are divided by significant political, cultural, ideological, ethnic and religious affiliation, with a tendency to move from time to time in the "subculture" politics, where the division turns into violence, as there is continuous violence in multiethnic countries, and in war, as it was the war of 2001.

Regarding the term consensual, in the etymological sense it is related to the Latin word "consentire", which means "to agree" or literally "to feel together," and in political sciences the term consensual is considered when all parties agree to accept something, thus, it is a medium in which a large majority of citizens agree on the major problems that the society faces, on the best type of government and on the solutions needed to address social issues.

The Republic of Macedonia was directly faced with this public policy for the first time in 2014 when the governing Albanian party DUI initiated the idea for a consensual candidate who would have broad support of the political parties. Its leader, Ali Ahmeti, said that "politicians are elected to bring responsible and courageous decisions, so political parties should show willingness to elect a consensual president who will represent worthily all communities and will engage with dignity for the country's Euro-Atlantic goals." The Albanian opposition parties DPA and NDP were not optimistic about the consensual candidate for president because according to them, the president of the state is a puppet institution and it is less important who will be in that position. Presidential elections have a meaning, always according to the Albanian opposition, if the President of the country is Albanian in order to transform Macedonia from a mono-ethnic country into a civic and multiethnic country. The concept of a consensual president has received support from some opposition Macedonian parties. The Alliance for Positive Macedonia supports the idea of consensual candidate and according to them "this initiative should be

supported by all political parties in the country, because if consensual election is installed in our political system, Macedonia will be much closer to European standards. The consensual president will help stabilize the political scene and coexistence.” The Liberal Party besides supporting the idea of a consensual president based on the model of neighboring countries, it also required that the president needs to be elected in the Assembly (Musliu, 2014). But the public opinion is divided into two camps regarding this discussion, where there are those who want the consensual president to be elected in the Assembly with the Badinter principle, and there are those who oppose the idea on the grounds that the aim of the institution President is to unite the will of the people and this is best accomplished with the free choice of the people and not from the Assembly.

In the end, we can conclude that today the Interfaith Cooperation Council, initiated and supported by President Trajkovski, is making slow progress, so there is a need of widening and deepening the support to interfaith dialogue. One of the options is the establishment of similar activities at low levels - regions or municipalities. Author Smock (2006: 33) points out that today there is a poor communication between religious communities, thus, despite the fact that all religious communities have sent official letters to each other, where the larger community makes an exception, that of Macedonian Orthodox Church, on the grounds that with the Ohrid Agreement and the initiation of interreligious dialogue, in the constitution of the Republic of Macedonia its status of being privileged is removed since it becomes equal with other religious communities that are a smaller in number.

The negligence of the proposal for consensual president from the largest party VMRO-DPMNE shows once again the failure of any kind of government attempts to stimulate interethnic and interreligious harmony.

This study shows that during the discussion regarding the consensual president, the candidate should not be a person who only has no hatred towards another ethnicity, but he/she must have a wide political, cultural and religious knowledge. The president is likely to have an important role in the interreligious and interethnic dialogue, but it certainly depends on his will, or more

specifically on his intellectual development, whether he is sociable with the world around him, whether he believes in peace and harmony in the world and above all whether he thinks beyond narrow party, ethnic, religious or ideological interests.

Based on the analysis so far, we conclude that if we analyze the last three presidents, the role of the best peacekeepers was played by President Trajkovski. If the consensual president cannot be elected in the Assembly in the future, as it is elected in many countries of the region and the world, and in turn, we make a comparison between the three presidents in the past, we come to a conclusion that the president closer to being a consensual president is President Trajkovski as he not only was the first who initiated the interfaith and interethnic dialogue, but he was the only one who did this successfully and had a great impact because he included all religious and ethnic communities in the dialogue without exception, unlike the situation of the organized conferences by both succeeding presidents that resulted with the dissatisfaction of the involved groups. One of the hypotheses why this president urged interethnic and interreligious dialogue in Macedonia is the fact that he did not belong to any of the major religions in the country, the Orthodox and Muslim, so he felt himself as an independent negotiator or a link between the two major communities that did not share their ethnicity or religion, between Orthodox Macedonians and Muslim Albanians, especially when one takes into account the fact that it was the time after the crisis. Hence, his neutral religious affiliation played an important role in promoting dialogue and we can therefore say that today the religion plays a determining role in resolving the political stalemates such as that of the consensual candidate, therefore, we say that religion needs to be one of the discussion points during the government coalition negotiations and beyond for the election of a consensual president. If the Macedonian side in the upcoming presidential elections would not accept a Muslim to be elected as a consensual president, the Albanian side needs to offer an alternative proposal where the consensual president needs to be an Orthodox Albanian, thus, even though he will be of Albanian ethnicity, what he will share with the major Macedonian party will be his Orthodox religious affiliation, relying of the case of President Trajkovski who was of Macedonian ethnicity but not an Orthodox as most of them, and it was a reason that he could have success in the interethnic dialogue; the case of an Orthodox Albanian

President will also be more convenient in relaxing ethnic and religious tensions as they will have in common his religious affiliation.

If no one takes into account this alternative which has the religious aspect of the consensual presidential candidate as a common point, then there is an opportunity of having a political stalemate as it happened in the last presidential elections in 2014 when the proposal of the Albanian party in government DUI was ignored by the government partner VMRO. DUI, as a sign of dissatisfaction and revolt for contempt, did not attend the Assembly session for the inauguration of the re-elected President Gjorge Ivanov, although they indirectly accepted Ivanov as President when the government coalition agreement with VMRO was reached, because he formally gives the government mandate.

In conclusion, we can say that the way in which this country was faced with the conflict of 2001 and vicissitudes that went for the dialogue and return of ethnic and religious cooperation with the help of internal and external factors, indicates that the country has only one way of solving problems, and that is dialogue. The culture of dialogue in our country can be one of our most genuine values.

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